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"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

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The connection between professional magazines and the research literature

Silvia Dobre*, Rachel Herbert* and Diana Hicks**

**s.dobre@elsevier.com; r.herbert@elsevier.com*

International Center for the Study of Research, Elsevier, Radarweg 29, Amsterdam, The Netherlands
Elsevier, The Boulevard, Langford Lane, Kidlington, Oxford, OX5 1GB, United Kingdom

***dhicks@gatech.edu*

School of Public Policy, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta GA, 30332-0345 (USA)

Introduction

In many technical areas, university research advances knowledge while a large profession practices in the community, often not in daily contact with universities. To advance both the profession and scientific field, research needs to inform practice and practice needs to inform research. Advancing science and practice depends on the ability to effectively transfer credible knowledge between the research and practitioner communities, and examining their literatures can provide insight into this process.

In this paper we analyse referencing in trade journals and magazines, media that circulates widely in the professional community and are extensively read. Do these magazines help convey the latest research to engineers, clinicians, architects and others? We explore the extent to which peer-reviewed journal publications are referenced in trade press and the characteristics of the referenced literature to establish the connection made between research and practice by this important segment of the technical publishing ecosystem.

Background

The challenges of connecting research and practice are of broad concern and have motivated research into evidence-based medicine, diffusion of innovation, societal impact of research, technology transfer and more. In scientometrics, alternative metrics of value for peer-reviewed papers have been explored including counts of Mendeley uploads, Tweets, and mentions in: blogs (Bornmann, 2015), newspapers (Begum et al. 2016), regulatory impact analyses (Desmarais and Hird, 2014), policy documents (Bornmann et al. 2016; Pinheiro et al. 2021; Szomszor & Adie, 2022; Vilkins & Grant, 2017), clinical trials documents (Thelwall and Kousha, 2016) a drug information database (Thelwall et al. 2017) and clinical practice guidelines (Grant et al. 2000; Kryl et al. 2012; Lewison & Sullivan, 2008; Thelwall and Maflahi, 2016). Counts of references in these documents are interesting because they signify broader societal interest in research output.

Here we extend this work to trade press. Professional journals and magazines have circulations orders of magnitude larger than academic journals. Subscriptions are often a benefit of professional society membership. Titles are also ad-supported and can be mailed out without requiring subscription. Often print copies of American titles reach over 100,000 professionals, and surveys show a substantial proportion of recipients read at least some of the material (Hicks, Melkers & Isett, 2019). Therefore, the information in trade press reaches practitioners and, presumably, informs practice. Therefore, trade press might provide a valuable pathway for research to reach application.

Method and Data

To investigate this possibility, we analysed the trade press indexed in Scopus. Elsevier defines trade press as serial publications covering, and intended to reach a specific type of business, in a magazine format, with articles on topical subjects, news items and advertisements that appeal to specialists in the field. Trade journals are seldom refereed and do not always have an editorial board. Abstracts are usually short or non-existent, and Elsevier states that “few or no references are given”. Trade press are included in Scopus because users and librarians consider selected articles to be scientifically relevant. Scopus indexes only articles or reviews of scientific relevance that are at least one page long and have at least one author (Elsevier, [Scopus Content Coverage Guide](#)).

We identified 803 trade journals using both Scopus sources and Ulrichs data. Across 2016 and 2021 (the six-year period of this study), the 363 journals which were active published 100,018 items that are indexed in Scopus: these comprise our dataset. We compiled their metadata, references and metadata of the articles that cite these trade press documents. References were found in 75% (271) of the active trade journals, and over the six-year period at least 50 items with references were indexed by Scopus from 33% (119) of the trade journals. Of the 100,018 indexed items, 28,303 have references. There are 425,810 references in total. Not all the referenced items are indexed in Scopus; for example, some references are simply URLs. 48% or 203,792 of the references are indexed in Scopus. Trade journals publishing the most articles containing references are: *Computer, Interactions* and *IEEE Consumer Electronics Magazine* in computing; *Pharmacy Times, US Pharmacist*, and *BioPharm International* in health care; *Power, Technology and Engineering, Corrosion* and *Indian Concrete Journal* in engineering. The trade press is not a homogeneous category. Therefore, using Ulrichs we refined our analysis by splitting the corpus into four types based on type of content, serial type, title and publisher. The four types are: professional journals, trade journals, trade magazines, and consumer magazines (Table 1).

Table 1: Characteristics of the four types of trade press

Trade Press Type	Characteristics
Professional Journals	Content type: Academic / Scholarly OR Publisher name includes "Institute", "Institution", "Profession", "Society"
Trade Journals	Content type: Trade; Serial type: Journal OR Serial Title includes "Journal" OR Publisher name includes "Association", "Federation"
Trade Magazines	Content type: Trade; Serial type: Magazine
Consumer Magazines	Content type: Consumer or Government; Serial type: Magazine, Newsletter, Bulletin or Newspaper

Figure 1 shows the number of serials, years indexed, and publications indexed in each category. Figure 2 identifies the publications make-up for each trade press sub-category. Here we begin to delineate the referencing patterns across the four types of trade press.

Figure 1: Description of the four categories of trade press

Figure 2: Proportions of publication type in the four categories of trade press

Results

The categories of trade press clearly differ in their intensity of referencing. Figure 3 shows the proportion of documents published in trade press containing references. Professional journals are the most heavily referenced, with 54% of documents containing references. Consumer magazines are the least reference intensive with only 5% of the documents containing references.

Figure 3: Proportion of documents in trade press category containing references

Articles containing references do not differ as much across categories, see Figure 4. In three of the four categories articles containing references list between 16 and 17 references on average. The exception is trade magazines where referencing articles average 11 references. The proportion of references indexed in Scopus ranges from 34% in consumer magazines to 52% in professional journals. The number of indexed references ranges from 5 to 9 references per article.

Figure 4: Average number of indexed and total references per article containing references

The substantial proportion of references that are indexed in Scopus suggests that the trade press does indeed reference academic material. Figure 5 confirms this. Peer-reviewed journal articles comprise, on average, 39% of references, with conference proceedings and books also

referenced. References to other trade press average 4% of references, slightly more in trade journals at 5%. Even in consumer magazines, 30% of references are to peer reviewed journal articles.

Figure 5: Distribution of trade press references

Conclusion

This preliminary exploration of the characteristics of the trade press lays the groundwork for our future analysis of patterns of impact of scholarly literature on professional literature. We have established that a substantial number of trade serials are indexed in Scopus, and so their references are accessible for analysis. We have argued that the trade press is not a homogeneous category and have identified meaningful dimensions on which titles differ. Finally, we have established that the trade press, even consumer magazines, does reference academic literature. The rich dataset that we have built promises to reveal important information about research that reaches application in professional work. We also intend to speak with the recipients of trade serials on their interaction with this knowledge to better understand this pathway and to validate these results.

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